

north american
academic research

Research

Lady Trainees with Baby in FTC: A Case Study of BPATC

Parimal Kumar Roy^{*1}, Jahid Siraz²

¹Deputy Director, Bangladesh Public Administration Training Centre, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

²PhD fellow, University of Malaya, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia

***Corresponding Author**

Accepted : 16 May 2019; Published online : 15 July, 2019

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3334947>

Abstract: Without foundations training, no officials will undergo training, which is mandated by the Bangladesh Public Administration Training Center (BPATC). Foundation Training Courses 64th & 65th batches as well as lady trainees, were chosen who had children and who were aged 1 to 3 years, while participating in a course; basically 25 female participants were deliberately taken to describe the abovementioned titles, "Lady trainee with the baby: BPATC case study." The average age of the mother trainees is 29.23 years, and the average age of the child is 15.28 months. As a public training institution, offering customers the facilities, the baby care center has been studied and the recommendations will contribute to the extension of the baby care center. To write this paper, a questionnaire was conducted in open and close form and two FGDs were conducted to search for clear concepts on the associated subjects. BPATC runs a baby care center to provide the facilities for lady trainees who, however, do not want to stay behind in comparison with their fellow trainees. To overcome the inconveniences of the mother trainee, BPATC has made such a huge effort and is never judged by the beneficiaries. The position of baby care center has been disclosed in this paper in the eye of the service recipient. What are the perceptions of BPATC, the baby care center and the course, were determined by interviews during the course. In addition, to validate the data, contact them by telephone. However, this number of customers is limited. In addition, the lessons learned will take steps to upgrade the services and help others to establish a childcare facility.

Keywords: Training, Baby care centre, BPATC, Lady Participants, Civil service.

Introduction

There will also be 27 cadres, and 25 cadres from the Bangladesh Public Administrative Training Center to take the foundation training (Mopa:2003;Ali:2010;Mozumder:2016;www.bpatc.org.bd:2018). After the 1971 liberation war, the civil service officer was trained at four institutions such as the Gazetted Officer Training Academy (GOTA), i.e. Renamed the Civil Service Officer Training Academy (COTA), the National Institute of Public Administration (NIPA),

and the Staff Training Institute (STI). BPATC starts her journey on 28 April, 1984 (Ali: 2010). However, BPATC is mandated for foundation training course (FTC), and also arranged other courses for additional secretary, Joint secretary, and Deputy Secretary. Apart from these, this center also arranged customized courses for her different clientele (www.bpatc.org.bd: 2019).

FTC is one of the main course and the new entrance officers suite. From the outset, participants of the lady were not allowed to join training with baby. Authority thinks that this training is rigorous. For this reason, a number of women officers are victimized by participation in training. In 24 years, BPATC will handle this matter through initiatives and set up a baby welfare center in 2008 (Moon: 2018). At that time, the different policies, like the PATC -2003, and BPATC evaluation policy-2013, have enhanced the participation of women in framework services; they are all drawn to the BPATC authority. The authority to run the course smoothly and give the chance to the lady officer with baby the same opportunity began to operate the Baby Care Centre. By that time, the participation of the women in the framework services was strengthened in a number of policy areas such as PATC 2003, which all drew the attention to the BPATC authority, and authority to run the course in an efficient manner, giving baby wom an equal opportunity.

Research settings and objectives

To taking or cooperation in establishment instructional class (FTC) which is sorted out by BPATC, it is a completely professional and compulsory course, it improves their ability as well as affirm their administration as a government workers for structure polished methodology of local officials of various dimension (PATP-2003). Bangladesh Public Administration Training Center (BPATC) is a pinnacle preparing foundation in open area the executives to prep up the wide range of government employees. BPATC is directing, still now extraordinary kinds of courses, for example, Foundation Training course (FTC) for newly recruited government employees; Advanced Course on Administration and Development (ACAD) for the Deputy Secretary, and equivalent officers in military division; Senior Staff Course (SSC) for Joint Secretary, and equal officer in military division; Policy Planning and Management Course (PPMC) for Additional Secretary, and Policy Dialogue (PD) for the Secretary and Senior Secretary to the legislature of Bangladesh. In this way, regarding the establishment instructional class which is comprised both female and male and considering the those woman participants who have 1 to 3 years issue and mean to arrive in a course alongside infant in BPATC for the half year long program. All the greater part of them multifaceted the issues with child. One side is - thorough day-long preparing, and then

again, infant is as a primary concern that is remaining in infant care focus with maidservant. Along these lines, mental predicament works in mother's brain while is going to in a class. In such manner, a woman learner's circumstance in preparing field is extraordinary, contrasting and male members, particularly those female course mates who did not have infant in the course. Thus, we should know the circumstance what sorts of issues they face and their recommendation to better progression in the preparation program in BPATC that claims as an apex organization in training sector in Bangladesh.

Still, presently ongoing 69th FTC (April 2019) in BPATC, time to time the FTC residency has been changed and now it is half year way. The background of the infant care focus has a tale. Multi decade prior, there was no infant care focus till 41st FTC. The participants who had child, they didn't participate in the course. In this result, these officers legged behind in taking preparing, affirming their activity and getting in track of profession advancement. In 2008, the BPATC, saw the truth and following the training strategy, permits the female officers straying with their child who is 1 to 3 years of age in the quarters to proceed with the establishment instructional class (Moon: 2018, Training Policy - 2003). Along these lines, it built up an infant care focus with one child on 12 October, 2008 from the 42nd establishment instructional class.

The general target of this investigation is by and large to recognize the discernments on preparing and preparing execution situation of the Lady students who were with child in BPATC. The connection among Participants and child taking consideration strategies to be portrayed in connection with working components in execution. This preparation is horrendously booked and a smidgen time to care for the issue who is being remained in day care focus with a family or female house cleaner. In this situation, it is hard to pack the brain in the class and to perform in other everyday exercises. Along these lines, to discover the investigation have decent variety, the accompanying explicit goals are to-

- know the conceptions of co-trainees towards the Lady trainees with baby.
- explore and mapping the problems during FTC Participants with baby.
- reviewing the rules and regulations of BPATC in relation to this unique group of people.
- recommending a practical ways to resolve the issue as well as open a venue for further research and scholars.

Problematize the topic and Conceptual framework

As a pinnacle preparing body it allows the child matured 12 to 36months (welcome letter of 65th FTC in 20017) ,with mother in BPATC. In any case, the child need to keep in the infant care focus in the day, the expense of that need to pay a tad cash .Although, this middle is very

financed by BPATC for allowing the chance to the woman students who have infant. The infant situation is restricted and served based on first come or signed on the enlistment. The kid is touchy issue and it needs mother's love to grow up easily. Then again, Training isn't a complimentary gift matter rather need to get testament. There have distinctive modules, physical exercise, examination, task, report, book audit, and introduction. In this way, lady trainees need to experience unbreakable work from day break to midnight. Establishment Training Course isn't just tireless put together work, yet in addition based with respect to studious. In these conditions, one mother feels weight on the both side. By thinking about the child wellbeing, she looks wellbeing and clean safe house, adequate sustenance and different comforts just as need compassion conduct from individual members. She needs rapidly and advances administrations from the concerned specialist from each corner. Be that as it may, the organization or course supervisory crew considers that woman learner is utilizing her tyke as an instrument to get more advantages. Be that as it may, Baby and Training both of are vital to a learner. To keeping up the psychological weight from youngster raising and scholarly weight is the difficulties to her. The two kinds of exercises, members feel anxiety and become sick. Anyway, what are the approaches to limit the issues for easily running FTC, if there should be an occurrence of woman learner with child?

Once more, BPATC is ordered for beefed the government workers sufficient in the worldwide world. Most female passageway officers are hitched and they participated in establishment instructional class with her first child. Since, BPATC have such office and can remain with parental figure. Additionally, it maybe impacts emphatically on her instructional class as well as on her tyke's physiological and mental advancement. Yet, the preparation strategies fall her on double job as - parenthood and student. The normal fulfillments go on rebellious and need to discover the arrangement ways. Along these lines, each lactating mother faces interesting difficulties in gathering her newborn child's requirements for sustenance and living settings amid the initial two years of life, because of mother's have the two jobs in the general public. We should address those ladies who have a high penchant to breastfeeding may pick occupations with offices that make it simpler to keep breastfeeding while at the same time working at the equivalent time. It is required an examination to investigate the components which are utilitarian for working lactating student mother in BPATC. It involves lament that BPATC does not have bosom sustaining corner despite the fact that her representatives. As a peak focus, it likewise does not has a place with a child or day care focus. Though just FTC members appreciate such kind of domain profits by advantages in return of giving extra paying. Another member, for example, ACAD, SSC and

other instructional class are denied of getting of that office. Subsequently, we should look through the standard of methodology to set up a child care place for all representatives and members and that will offer fuel to set up an infant care focus to different institutions.

Preparing is an uncommon exercises and new condition to mother and youngster is tough to manage suddenly. However, they live in uninhibited settings yet the psychological fulfillment is an issue to live for the up and coming days. To outline the inquired about field, I have utilized SWOT examination structure. Since, BPATC has a heritage to prepare the participant's officer as well as the most extreme government workers. By considering the members sees on its Strengths, Weakness, Threats, and Opportunity to be examined with regards to infant care focus execution and Training Policy. In spite of the fact that the preparation strategy and BPATC Policy demonstrates to make a viable, creative, responsible, straightforward, and genuine officer to serve the general population .With regards to members' thought, we get the accompanying issues on SWOT grid-

Strength	Weakness	Opportunity	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Well guard institution. - Welled Infrastructure. - Tight security. - Training policy - Large space / play ground - Single room. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No child specialist and Psychologist - No medicine available. - No budget from BPATC - No training & development to the caregiver. - Caregiver and baby ratio is not logical. - No have breastfeeding corner and scope to do it while training period. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Baby care centre can be upgraded - sufficient logistics - available manpower - Govt. is positive on gender and child issues. - having scope to redesign curriculum and reschedule class time. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sneaks / Bush - Diseases as - Dengue, Chikunnunia, - Damp and shady baby care.

Methodology

The investigation was directed through open and shut finished poll meeting of the took an interest participants who were with infant. Additionally, two FGD was completed for the better understanding the feelings of hatred with preparing in BPATC. Two groups 64 FTC (

beginning 24 May 2017 to closure 19 November 2017) and 65 FTC (beginning period 06 august 2017 to completion 01 February 2018) both are chosen for inspecting, all out 624 officers were taken an interest in the preparation program in 2017-2018. Essentially course period, I gathered the data. All officers were comprised of female and male just as various frameworks. Among the Participants 12 and 13 learners were with child in BPATC, in separate bunch. In this way, uninhibitedly test measure was 25 members, those were purposively chosen. Interviewing the female members, yet in addition course management team individuals, BPATC the executives part just as the parental figures additionally met for getting the reasonable ideas. As an optional information, assembled distinctive sorts of reports, provided recorded information by establishment course office, and individuals feelings are additionally dissected as subjective information.

Results and Discussion

Profile of the respondents.

By thinking about various frameworks, ages, family establishes, legal administrations (Bangladesh Judicial Services), I pick the respondents. Chosen learners are mother and sex one-sided is restrained to the exploration. The example number is established of 06 frameworks and 01 service. The age gathering of the respondents was classified into three gatherings and they were 25 to 30, 31 to 35, lastly 36 to 40 years. All respondents enter to the administration under age of 30, and a large portion of them have a child in the wake of entering in to the administration. It portrays that 72 % learners have a place with 25-30 gathering, the rest rate 28 % respondents were under 31 – 35 gathering. However, 36 - 40 bunches did not hold any number of respondents.

Figure-1: Age group of the respondents' lady trainees with baby.

Among the respondents, 40 % respondents are from administration cadre, and the second most respondents is 36 % in agricultural cadre. Only 4 % respondents means one trainees belongs to Bangladesh judicial service and other cadres such as information, fisheries, forest

and Forestry follow the judicial service in number. Although Public works cadre exist 8 % trainees in the training program.

Figure-2: Trainee mothers' service enrollment in FTC.

Study reveals the family size of the respondents. Most participants like to stay with own self. 14 families are unique and other 11 is the joint. So, figure -3 Shows that 80 % participants have 3 to 5 family members and only 20 % Trainees have 6 to 8 family members.

Figure -3: Respondents family size in FTC

Child age

As per welcome letter of 65th FTC, any participants can bring the child to BPATC with her if the child become aged 12 to 36 months. I categorized the child aged into 4. First one is 12 to 18 months, second one is 19 to 24 month, third one is 25 to 30 month , and finally fourth one is 31 to 36 month. The figure reveals that 12 to 18 months group belongs the 72 %, 8% child age is 19 to 24 months. 12 % baby bear the age 25 to 30 months, and 31 to 36 month group child age is 8%.

Figure -4: Respondent's Child age

Ailing issues on baby and mother

By contemplating different systems, ages, family sets up, lawful organizations (Bangladesh Judicial Services), I pick the respondents. Picked students are mother and sex uneven is controlled to the investigation. The model number is built up of 06 structures and 01service. The age social occasion of the respondents was arranged into three get-togethers and they were 25 to 30, 31 to 35, in conclusion 36 to 40 years. All respondents enter to the organization under age of 30, and a huge segment of them have a tyke in the wake of entering in to the organization. It depicts that 72 % students have a spot with 25-30 assembling; the rest rate 28 % respondents were under 31 – 35 gathering. Be that as it may, 36 - 40 groups did not hold any number of respondents.

Breast feeding scenario.

Bosom encouraging to her tyke is inescapable to keep sound youngster wellbeing. Just 7 respondents educated that they are not associated with bosom sustaining, in spite of the fact that 18 learners are continued breastfeeding. One female student did not have any desire to reveal this disposition. In addition, likewise the investigation demonstrates that 6 respondents communicated the child care offices are adequate and 17 respondents demonstrated their hatred on infant care centre.02 students declined to do any remarks in such manner. Genuinely, all members who are habituated in breastfeeding practice, they show that this preparation action damaged the breastfeeding practice to the tyke, and they proposed in such manner to the course supervisory group ought to rework the class plan for rehearsing this movement.

Expected result on final passing out.

After fruition the half year course, last going out outcome brings out on the end day. We like to allude the normal outcome is the hold a situation in the legitimacy list. The assessment

branch of BPATC readies a legitimacy list and 10% members of absolute members by and large get commonplace as exemplary members, and they send to presentation visit in outside nation. 40 % members expected to hold a legitimacy position, 56% learners believed that they will be cheerful on the off chance that they get testament. The rest 4% woman student about on fear in the passing test. In spite of the fact that, I inspected the outcomes in the wake of revealing that, no one got held the situation just as nobody bombed in the last passing. This situation uncovers that child made the psychological strain to approaching the going out outcome.

Baby birth: NVD vs CS

20 child was caesarian (CS), and the rest number of that is 5 infant was conveyed typically (NVD). Most of the infant is CS and they have relations to distress. Fundamentally, CS infant become delicate and effectively they can't adapt to antagonistic circumstance, in examination with ordinary infant. All moms are post graduated. Most members are CS mother and Education did not affect on typical conveyance. Not just that all infants are the principal issue, and 20 is the CS. Thus, 23 babies become sick and troubled the student mother.

Food and living

In the day time, infant remain with house cleaner in the child care focus yet in the night mother took it with claim room. In the BPATC rule, a mother gets a solitary room and two beds. Most moms alleviate that the sustenance framework isn't great and clean. Subsequently child turns out to be sick. Additionally, the lounge room isn't solid and did not adequate light and air to live easily. BPATC did not take the foodliability for infant and its chaperon. To keep up the nourishment for infant and youngster, they need to buy basic supply utensils and need to cook for them as per decisions of female members. Now and then, the guardians consume the feast while cooking, by sitting in front of the TV. In this reaction, two members requested to expel Television from the child care room.

Participants' perception on overall baby care facilities.

Baby care past one decade and its amenities are failed to meetup the participants' desires. Only 20 % thought, facilities are sufficient but 68% thought the insufficient services or facilities, 12% declined to give the answer in this regard.

Co-trainees' feeling on baby and mother.

Nobody member communicated the sorrow going to the co-members and their youngster was ever dismissed by the kindred students. Two FGDs and met demonstrated that 100 % learner, even male members, were indicated great conduct, and did the carry on with helpful personality to mother and youngster.

Rethinking the baby care centre: some recommendations

"A few things, never truly change" picked from Luthans (2005). Mother and kid connection is one of that never show signs of change. In this situation, state should notice on woman learner who wishes to participate in the training program. Time to time 1 to 41 FTC officially gone and woman members were denied of getting open door with infant. At last, the issue is disintegrated yet need to support redesign. Be that as it may, the service of open organization (MOPA) is the directing point to run the government workers. It has been detailed a preparation arrangement in 2003, naming-Bangladesh Public Administration Training Policy-2003. This strategy did not demonstrate about on woman student whom have child. However, BPATC, as of claim command and able leadership, they set up a minor child care community for considering the profession mother. The members feelings of hatred their exercises by putting down certain suggestions. All are turned out to be amazed that it is giving average luxuries whether it guarantees as pinnacle. Most issues might be settled if the course supervisory group takes care of the issues with compassionate view. Be that as it may, their proposals are in the accompanying to amoralities the middle---

- Room should have sufficient light and air.
- Pediatrician should have appointed.
- Medicine are to be supplied available
- Caregivers should have professional attitude and required training on this issue.
- Curriculum design should rearrange and mothers should give privilege for breast feeding.
- Cleansing activity should run regularly.
- Toy and Toys should supply available.
- Should have install close circuit camera in the baby care centre.
- Baby care supporting staffs need training to handle the baby care Centre.
- Should remove the TV from the baby care room.
- Should supply sufficient gas burner and fridge.
- One care take for three babies, should maintain this proportionate.
- Transparency in rule and have to establish accountability in all spheres.
- It should keep optional participation to sports session on afternoon for mother trainee.
- Breastfeeding corner have to set up and have to give the time for doing this.

- Typical systems have to change in all spheres.
- Cooking facilities have to increase in the baby care centre.

References

1. Ali , AHM Shawkat (2010) Civil Service Management in Bangladesh. UPL, Dhaka.
2. Luthans, Fred (2005) Organizational Behavior Macgraw Hill, Singapore.
3. Mozumder, AKM ,Abdul Awal (2016) History of Bangladesh Civil Service (Bangla) Mukta Chinta Prokashoni, Dhaka.
4. Moon , Dr. Sk.Muslima (2018) A study on strength and limitation of Baby care centre for female participants of FTC courses at BPATC (unpublished) Seminar paper of 120th ACAD, BPATC.
5. Ministry of Public Administration (MOPA: 2003) Public Administration Training Policy
6. www.bpatc.org.bd
7. www.mopa.gov.bd

Parimal Kumar Roy

Hon's and Masters in Anthropology, and did second Masters in Business administration. He is currently faculty member in Bangladesh Public Administration Training Centre, Dhaka. His teaching areas are - project management, cultural ecology, Bangladesh, history society and culture, and training policy etc.

Jahid Siraz

Hon's and Masters in Anthropology. He is now PhD fellow in Malaya University, Malaysia. He is freelance anthropologist, also ex – faculty member in Shahjalal University of Science and Technology Sylhet, Bangladesh. Now doing research in methodology for indigenous knowledge system.

© 2019 by the authors. TWASP, NY, USA . Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

